

Minimum Energy Estimation and Moving Horizon Estimation

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Abstract—Minimum Energy Estimation is a way of filtering the state of a nonlinear system from partial and inexact measurements. It is a generalization of Gauss’ method of least squares. Its application to filtering of control systems goes back at least to Mortenson who called it Maximum Likelihood Estimation [12]. For linear, Gaussian systems it reduces to maximum likelihood estimation (aka Kalman Filtering) but this is not true for nonlinear systems. We prefer the name Minimum Energy Estimation (MEE) that was introduced by Hijab [4]. Both Mortenson and Hijab dealt with systems in continuous time, we extend their methods to discrete time systems and show how power series techniques can lessen the computational burden.

Moving Horizon Estimation (MHE) is a moving window version of MEE. It computes the solution to an optimal control problem over a past moving window that is constrained by the actual observations on the window. The optimal state trajectory at the end of the window is the MEE estimate at this time. The cost in the optimal control problem is usually taken to be an L2 norm of the three slack variables; the initial condition noise, the driving noise and the measurement noise. MHE requires the buffering of the measurements over the past window. The optimal control problem is solved in real time by a nonlinear program solver but it becomes more difficult as the length of the window is increased.

The power series approach to MME can be applied to MHE and this permits the choice of a very short past window consisting of one time step. This speeds up MHE and allows its real time implementation on faster processes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Consider a discrete time nonlinear system

$$\begin{aligned} x^+ &= f(t, x, u) \\ y &= h(t, x, u) \\ x(0) &= x^0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where the state $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$, the control $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times 1}$, the measurement $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times 1}$ and $x^+(t) = x(t+1)$. The filtering problem is to estimate $x(t)$ from $u(s), 0 \leq s \leq t-1$, from $y(s), 1 \leq s \leq t-1$ and from some inexact knowledge about x^0 . We denote this estimate by $\hat{x}(t|t-1)$. We also consider estimating $x(t)$ using the additional measurement $y(t)$, we denote this estimate $\hat{x}(t|t)$.

The standard approach is add noises to the model, a driving noise $v(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times 1}$, an observation noise $w(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times 1}$ and an initial condition noise $\tilde{x}^0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x^+ &= f(t, x, u) + g(t, x, u)v \\ y &= h(t, x, u) + w \\ x(0) &= \hat{x}^0 + \tilde{x}^0 \end{aligned}$$

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where \hat{x}^0 is our estimate of $x(0)$ based on prior information.

The stochastic version of this approach is to assume that $v(t)$ and $w(t)$ are independent, white Gaussian noise processes and \tilde{x}^0 is an independent Gaussian random vector of mean zero and known covariance.. Then the conditional density of the state given the past controls $u(s), 0 \leq s \leq t-1$ and past measurements $y(s), 1 \leq s \leq t-1$ satisfies an integral-differential-difference equation that is very difficult to solve. About the only time it can be solved is when the system is linear for then the conditional density is Gaussian and its mean and covariance can be computed by a Kalman filter.

The minimum energy version of this approach is to assume the noises are deterministic but unknown. One finds the noise triple that minimizes

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\|\tilde{z}^0\|^2 + \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \|v(s)\|^2 + \sum_{s=1}^t \|w(s)\|^2 \right) \quad (2)$$

subject to

$$\begin{aligned} z^+ &= f(s, z, u) + g(s, z, u)v \\ y &= h(s, z, u) + w \\ z(0) &= \hat{x}^0 + \tilde{z}^0 \end{aligned}$$

where $u(s), 0 \leq s \leq t-1$ and $y(s), 1 \leq s \leq t-1$ are the actual control and measurement sequences. Then the MME is $\hat{x}(t|t) = z(t)$. The heuristic behind MME is that (2) (or some variant) is the energy in the noise triple. Nature in her attempt to confuse us chooses the three noises in a parsimonious fashion consistent with the past controls and past measurements. If the system is linear then MME filtering is identical to Kalman filtering provided that the weights of the norms in (2) are the inverses of covariances of the noises in the stochastic version.

It has been shown that under suitable conditions the continuous time MME is globally convergent [7]. that is, the MME estimate converges to the state of the model (Iregardless of the initial conditions of the model and the filter. We conjecture that a similar result holds for discrete time MEE.

II. MME FUNCTIONAL EQUATIONS

Since we know $u(t)$ we can simplify notation by redefining

$$\begin{aligned} f(t, x) &= f(t, x, u(t)) \\ g(t, x) &= g(t, x, u(t)) \\ h(t, x) &= h(t, x, u(t)) \end{aligned}$$

We can extend the MME technique by minimizing a more general form of the energy using only measurements to time $\tau \leq t$ subject to a terminal condition,

$$\pi(x, t|\tau) = \min_{z^0, v} \left\{ \alpha^t \pi^0(z^0) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \alpha^{t-s} \|v(s)\|_{Q(s)}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=1}^{\tau} \alpha^{t-s} \|w(s)\|_{R(s)}^2 \right\} \quad (3)$$

subject to

$$z^+ = f(s, z(s)) + g(s, z(s))v(s) \quad (4)$$

$$y(s) = h(s, z) + w(s) \quad (5)$$

$$z(0) = z^0 \quad (6)$$

where $y(s)$ are the actual observations and the additional terminal condition

$$z(t) = x \quad (7)$$

The forgetting factor is $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $\pi^0(z^0)$ is a nonnegative definite function of z^0 and

$$\|v(s)\|_{Q(s)}^2 = v'(s)Q(s)v(s)$$

$$\|w(s)\|_{R(s)}^2 = w'(s)R(s)w(s)$$

The smaller the forgetting factor the more weight is place on the most recent observations.

We assume that $Q(s) > 0$, $R(s) > 0$ but one can consider more general MEE techniques of minimizing

$$\pi(x, t|\tau) = \min_{z^0, v} \left\{ \alpha^t \pi^0(z^0) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=0}^{t-1} \alpha^{t-s} l(s, v(s), w(s)) \right\}$$

where $l(s, v, w)$ is positive definite in v, w subject to (4, 5, 6, 7) but we don't do so here.

The MEE is given by

$$\hat{x}(t|\tau) = \operatorname{argmin}_x \pi(x, t|\tau) \quad (8)$$

We are primarily interested in the cases where $\tau = t - 1$ or $\tau = t$.

Filtering of a discrete time system is usually done in two alternating steps. In MEE the prediction step starts with $\hat{x}(t|t)$ and $\pi(x, t|t)$ and computes $\hat{x}(t+1|t)$ and $\pi(x, t+1|t)$ by a solving functional equation for π of dynamic programming type,

$$\pi(x, t+1|t) = \min_{z, v} \left\{ \alpha \pi(z, t|t) + \frac{1}{2} \|v(t)\|_{Q(t)}^2 \right\} \quad (9)$$

subject to the constraint

$$x = f(t, z) + g(t, z)v \quad (10)$$

The predicted estimate $\hat{x}(t+1|t)$ is given by

$$\hat{x}(t+1|t) = \operatorname{argmin}_x \pi(x, t+1|t) \quad (11)$$

When $y(t)$ becomes known the MEE assimilation step is given by the functional equation,

$$\pi(x, t|t) = \pi(x, t|t-1) + \frac{1}{2} \|y(t) - h(t, x)\|_{R(t)}^2 \quad (12)$$

and the assimilated estimate $\hat{x}(t|t)$ is

$$\hat{x}(t|t) = \operatorname{argmin}_x \pi(x, t|t) \quad (13)$$

First the prediction step is applied at $t = 0$ to $\pi(x, 0|0) = \pi^0(x)$ and $\hat{x}(0|0) = \operatorname{argmin}_x \pi^0(x)$ to get $\pi(x, 1|0)$ and $\hat{x}(1|0)$. Then the assimilation step yields $\pi(x, 1|1)$ and $\hat{x}(1|1)$, etc.

If $\pi^0(x)$ has multiple local minima then at each one a MEE filter is initiated similar to [6]. If there are k local minima then we have $\hat{x}^j(t|\tau)$, $\pi^j(x, t|\tau)$, for $j = 1, \dots, k$. In effect the MEE filter becomes a particle filter $\hat{x}^1(t|\tau), \dots, \hat{x}^k(t|\tau)$ with weights $\pi^1(\hat{x}^1(t|\tau), t|\tau), \dots, \pi^k(\hat{x}^k(t|\tau), t|\tau)$ indicating the reliability of each estimate. The best estimate is $\hat{x}^j(t|\tau)$ where

$$\pi^j(x, t|\tau) = \min_i \pi^i(\hat{x}^i(t|\tau), t|\tau)$$

This bifurcation into multiple filters can also take place at a later time if $\pi(x, t|\tau)$ has multiple local minima.

III. PREDICTION STEP

The prediction step starts with $\hat{x}(t|t)$ and $\pi(x, t|t)$ and computes $\hat{x}(t+1|t)$ and $\pi(x, t+1|t)$. We attach the constraint (10) to the criterion (9) with a Lagrange multiplier $\lambda(t, x) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ to get a family of unconstrained minimization problems indexed by t and x ,

$$\min_{z, v, \lambda} \left\{ \alpha \pi(z, t|t) + \frac{1}{2} \|v\|_{Q(t)}^2 + \lambda'(t, x) (x - f(t, z) - g(t, z)v) \right\} \quad (14)$$

To get the first order necessary conditions we set to zero the partials of this quantity with respect to z, v, λ .

Setting the partial of (14) with respect to λ to zero yields the constraint (10).

Setting the partial of (14) with respect to v to zero yields

$$0 = v'Q(t) - \lambda'(t, x)g(t, z)$$

Because $Q(t)$ is assumed to be invertible this can be solved for $v(t, z, x)$ as a function of λ

$$v(t, z, x) = Q^{-1}(t)g'(t, z)\lambda(t, x) \quad (15)$$

Then the constraint (10) becomes

$$x = f(t, z) + g(t, z)Q^{-1}(t)g'(t, z)\lambda(t, x) \quad (16)$$

Setting the partial of (14) with respect to z to zero yields

$$0 = \alpha \frac{\partial \pi}{\partial z}(z, t|t) - \lambda'(t, x) \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial z}(t, z) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (g(t, z)v(t, z, x)) \right)$$

Because of (15) this becomes

$$0 = \alpha \frac{\partial \pi}{\partial z}(z, t|t) - \lambda'(t, x) \frac{\partial f}{\partial z}(t, z) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\lambda'(t, x)g(t, z)Q^{-1}(t)g'(t, z)\lambda(t, x)) \quad (17)$$

So at each time t and each state x we must solve the two nonlinear equations (16, 17) in the two unknowns

$z(t, x)$, $\lambda(t, x)$. Then (15) yields $v(t, z(t, x), x)$ and we can compute $\pi(x, t+1|t)$ and $\hat{x}(t+1|t)$ from

$$\pi(x, t+1|t) = \alpha\pi(z(t, x), t|t) + \frac{1}{2}\|v(t, z(t, x), x)\|_{Q(t)}^2 \quad (18)$$

$$\hat{x}(t+1|t) = \operatorname{argmin}_x \pi(x, t+1|t) \quad (19)$$

Solving these equations is a daunting task so we turn to a series approach. For simplicity of exposition we assume $g(t, z) = G(t)$. The general case is more complicated but it follows in a similar fashion. To simplify notation let

$$\bar{Q}(t) = G(t)Q^{-1}(t)G'(t)$$

We start by expanding f and π in series in $\tilde{z} = z - \hat{x}(t|t)$,

$$f(t, z) = f^{[0]}(t) + F(t)\tilde{z} + f^{[2]}(t, \tilde{z}) + \dots$$

$$\pi(z, t|t) = \pi^{[0]}(t|t) + \frac{1}{2}\tilde{z}'P(t)\tilde{z} + \pi^{[3]}(\tilde{z}, t|t) + \dots$$

where $^{[d]}$ denotes a homogeneous polynomial term of degree d in \tilde{z} .

The minimum of $\pi(x, t|t)$ occurs at $\hat{x}(t|t)$ so (9) implies that $\pi(x, t+1|t) \geq \alpha\pi(\hat{x}(t|t), t|t)$ for all x . On the other hand from (9, 10) with $v(t) = 0$ we see that $\pi(f(t, \hat{x}(t|t)), t+1|t) \leq \alpha\pi(\hat{x}(t|t), t|t)$. So the minimum of $\pi(x, t+1|t)$ occurs at $f(t, \hat{x}(t|t))$,

$$\hat{x}(t+1|t) = f(t, \hat{x}(t|t)) = f^{[0]}(t) \quad (20)$$

We expand \tilde{z} and λ in series in $\tilde{x} = x - \hat{x}(t+1|t)$,

$$\tilde{z}(t, x) = Z(t)\tilde{x} + z^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x}) + z^{[3]}(t, \tilde{x}) + \dots$$

$$\lambda(t, x) = \Lambda(t)\tilde{x} + \lambda^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x}) + \lambda^{[3]}(t, \tilde{x}) + \dots$$

Then the constraint (16) becomes

$$\tilde{x} = f(t, z) - f^{[0]}(t) + \bar{Q}(t)\lambda(t, x) \quad (21)$$

and (17) becomes

$$0 = \alpha \frac{\partial \pi}{\partial z}(z, t|t) - \lambda'(t, x) \frac{\partial f}{\partial z}(t, z) \quad (22)$$

We collect from these equations (21) and (22) the terms linear in \tilde{x} to obtain

$$\tilde{x} = F(t)Z(t)\tilde{x} + \bar{Q}(t)\Lambda(t)\tilde{x}$$

$$0 = \alpha P(t|t)Z(t)\tilde{x} - F'(t)\Lambda(t)\tilde{x}$$

These equations must hold for any \tilde{x} so $Z(t), \Lambda(t)$ satisfy

$$\begin{bmatrix} I \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \mathcal{H}(t) \begin{bmatrix} Z(t) \\ \Lambda(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

where

$$\mathcal{H}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} F(t) & \bar{Q}(t) \\ \alpha P(t|t) & -F'(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

The solvability of these equations depends on the invertibility of $\mathcal{H}(t)$ which discuss in a later section.

Assuming $\mathcal{H}(t)$ is invertible, we collect the second order terms in \tilde{x} from (21) and (22),

$$\mathcal{H}(t) \begin{bmatrix} z^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x}) \\ \lambda^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x}) \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} k^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x}) \\ l^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x}) \end{bmatrix}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} k^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x}) &= f^{[2]}(t, Z(t)\tilde{x}) \\ l^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x}) &= \alpha \left(\frac{\partial \pi^{[3]}}{\partial z}(t, Z(t)\tilde{x}) \right)' \\ &\quad - \left(\frac{\partial f^{[2]}}{\partial z}(t, Z(t)\tilde{x}) \right)' \Lambda(t)\tilde{x} \end{aligned}$$

Again the solvability of these equations depends on the invertibility of $\mathcal{H}(t)$.

The degree three terms in (21) and (22) are

$$\mathcal{H}(t) \begin{bmatrix} z^{[3]}(t, \tilde{x}) \\ \lambda^{[3]}(t, \tilde{x}) \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} k^{[3]}(t, \tilde{x}) \\ l^{[3]}(t, \tilde{x}) \end{bmatrix}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} k^{[3]}(t, \tilde{x}) &= f^{[3]}(t, Z(t)\tilde{x}) \\ &\quad + \left(f^{[2]}(t, Z(t)\tilde{x}) + z^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x}) \right)^{[2]} \\ l^{[3]}(t, \tilde{x}) &= \alpha \left(\left(\frac{\partial \pi^{[3]}}{\partial z}(t, Z(t)\tilde{x} + z^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x})) \right)^{[3]} \right)' \\ &\quad + \alpha \left(\frac{\partial \pi^{[4]}}{\partial z}(t, Z(t)\tilde{x}) \right)' \\ &\quad - \left(\frac{\partial f^{[2]}}{\partial z}(t, Z(t)\tilde{x}) \right)' \lambda^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x}) \\ &\quad - \left(\frac{\partial f^{[2]}}{\partial z}(t, z^{[2]}(t, \tilde{x})) \right)' \Lambda(t)\tilde{x} \\ &\quad - \left(\frac{\partial f^{[3]}}{\partial z}(t, Z(t)\tilde{x}) \right)' \Lambda(t)\tilde{x} \end{aligned}$$

and $(\cdot)^{[d]}$ indicates the degree d terms of the enclosed expression. The higher degree terms are found in a similar fashion.

Suppose we have found \tilde{z} and λ in series in \tilde{x} to degree d then (15) yields an expansion of $v(t, z, x)$ to degree d in \tilde{x} . We plug this into (18) and assuming $\pi(x, t|t)$ is of degree $d+1$ we obtain an expansion of $\pi(x, t+1|t)$ to degree $d+1$ in $\tilde{x} = x - \hat{x}(t+1|t)$. The argminimum $\hat{x}(t+1|t)$ of $\pi(x, t+1|t)$ with respect to x is given by (20). This completes the prediction step.

If $d=1$ the part of prediction step (20) from $\hat{x}(t|t)$ to $\hat{x}(t+1|t)$ is the same as that of the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) [3]. But the part of prediction step (14) from $P(t|t)$ to $P(t+1|t)$ is not the same as that of the EKF. The EKF prediction is

$$P(t+1|t) = F(t)P(t|t)F'(t) + G(t)G'(t)$$

IV. ASSIMILATION STEP

The assimilation step starts with $y(t)$, $\hat{x}(t|t-1)$ and a degree $d+1$ polynomial approximation to $\pi(x, t|t-1)$ expanded in $x - \hat{x}(t|t-1)$ and computes $\hat{x}(t|t)$ and a degree $d+1$ polynomial approximation to $\pi(x, t|t)$ given by (12).

To compute $\hat{x}(t|t)$ given by (13) we assume that the polynomial $\pi(x, t|t)$ is strictly convex in x in a neighborhood around $\hat{x}(t|t-1)$ and that $\hat{x}(t|t)$ is in this neighborhood. So

we can use Newton's method to minimize (13) with initial guess $\hat{x}(t|t-1)$. The argminimum is $\hat{x}(t|t)$. Then $\pi(x, t|t-1)$ is transformed into a polynomial of degree $d+1$ in the new $\tilde{x} = x - \hat{x}(t|t)$. This completes the assimilation step.

V. SOLVABILITY OF THE SERIES EQUATIONS

We have seen the the series equations are solvable if (23) is invertible and (23) looks like the Hamiltonian matrix of a continuous time LQR problem.

Consider the problem of minimizing

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty \xi' M \xi + \nu' N \nu \, dt$$

subject to

$$\dot{\xi} = A\xi + B\nu$$

The control Hamiltonian for this problem is

$$\bar{\mathcal{H}}(\zeta, \xi, \nu) = \zeta'(A\xi + B\nu) + \frac{1}{2}(\xi' M \xi + \nu' N \nu)$$

where ζ is the adjoint variable. The optimal control $\nu = \nu(\zeta, \xi)$ is found by setting to zero the partial of $\bar{\mathcal{H}}$ with respect to ν . This yields

$$\nu = -N^{-1}B'\zeta$$

and the Hamiltonian is

$$\bar{\mathcal{H}}(\zeta, \xi, \nu(\zeta, \xi)) = \zeta'A'\xi + \frac{1}{2}(\xi' M \xi - \zeta' B N^{-1} B' \zeta)$$

The Hamilton equations are

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\xi} &= \frac{\partial \bar{\mathcal{H}}(\zeta, \xi, \nu(\zeta, \xi))}{\partial \zeta} = A\xi - B'N^{-1}B\zeta \\ \dot{\zeta} &= -\frac{\partial \bar{\mathcal{H}}(\zeta, \xi, \nu(\zeta, \xi))}{\partial \xi} = -A'\zeta - M\xi \end{aligned}$$

or in matrix form with the variables in reverse order

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\zeta} \\ \dot{\xi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -A' & -M \\ -BN^{-1}B' & A \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \zeta \\ \xi \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

The eigenvalues of the Hamiltonian matrix in (24) will all be off the imaginary axis if A, B is stabilizable and $M^{1/2}, A$ is detectable where $M = (M^{1/2})'M^{1/2}$.

We recognize that the negative of the Hamiltonian matrix in (24) is equal to (23) if

$$\begin{aligned} A' &= F(t) \\ M &= \bar{Q}(t) = G(t)Q^{-1}(t)G'(t) \\ B'N^{-1}B &= \alpha P(t|t) \end{aligned}$$

So $M^{1/2}, A$ detectable is equivalent to $F(t), G(t)$ stabilizable since $Q^{-1}(t)$ is invertible and A, B stabilizable is equivalent to $\alpha P^{1/2}(t|t), F(t)$ detectable. If $P(0|0)$ is positive definite then so is every $P(t|t)$ so trivially $\alpha P^{1/2}(t|t), F(t)$ detectable. So we have proven the following.

Theorem Suppose that $P(0|0)$ is positive definite and at each $t \geq 0$, the pair $F(t), G(t)$ is stabilizable then $\mathcal{H}(t)$ given by (23) is invertible for each $t \geq 0$.

VI. MINIMUM HORIZON ESTIMATION

Minimum Horizon Estimation (MHE) is Minimum Energy Estimation over a moving window. It is the dual of Model Predictive Control (MPC). Like MPC it is usually done in real time and yields real time estimates of the current state.

Here is a simple description on MHE. For a more comprehensive description see [2], [14], [15]. Again the system model is

$$\begin{aligned} x^+ &= f(t, x, u) \\ y &= h(t, x, u) \end{aligned}$$

One chooses a window length T . We seek to estimate $x(t)$ from the observations $y(t-T+1), \dots, y(t)$ over the past window and our estimate $\hat{x}(t-T|t-T)$ of $x(t-T)$. We minimize

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{z^{t-T}, v, w} & \left\{ \|z^{t-T} - \hat{x}(t-T|t-T)\|_{P(t-T)}^2 \right. \\ & \left. + \sum_{s=t-T}^{t-1} \|v(s)\|_{Q(s)}^2 + \sum_{s=t-T+1}^t \|w(s)\|_{R(s)}^2 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

subject to

$$\begin{aligned} z^+ &= f(s, z, u) + g(s, z, u)v \\ y &= h(s, z, u) + w \end{aligned}$$

where $u(s)$ is the actual input and $y(s)$ is the actual output. The MHE estimate is

$$\hat{x}(t|t) = z(t)$$

where $z(s)$ is the minimizing state trajectory.

This minimization problem is solved in real time by a nonlinear program solver. The state estimate is passed to an MPC algorithm which computes $u(t)$ by solving in real time a second nonlinear program. Needless to say the two nonlinear programs need to be solved in a small fraction of one time step so the latest observation $y(t)$ quickly yields the desired $u(t)$. Then the process is repeated at time $t+1$. The complexity of the MHE nonlinear program is dictated by the nonlinearities of f, g, h and the length of the past observation window, T . There is not much we can do about f, h as they are given by the plant and we can take g constant as we did before. So the question is can we shorten T and still get reasonable estimates.

We believe that the power series techniques described above will allow us to make T as short as 1 time step. The first modification is instead of taking a fixed past window of length T we use the whole past but with a forgetting factor $0 < \alpha < 1$.

Assuming that $\hat{x}(t-1|t-1)$ and $\pi(x, t-1, |t-1)$ have been computed at time $t-1$ then one prediction step is taken before time t and then at time t when $y(t)$ becomes available an assimilation step is taken. No nonlinear program needs to be solved and most of the computational load is in the prediction step which has the whole time interval between $t-1$ and t to be completed.

Fig. 1. Typical Trajectory

Fig. 3. $\tilde{x}_1(t|t)$

Fig. 2. Typical Phase Portrait

Fig. 4. $x(t)$ blue, $\hat{x}(t|t)$ red

But one drawback of this approach is that assumes the system is smooth with no active constraints. If these assumptions don't hold then one needs to go to a patchy approach [13], [5] which we will report on at a later date.

VII. EXAMPLE

Here is the Euler discretion of the Van der Pol Oscillator with time step 0.1 second,

$$\begin{aligned} x_1^+ &= x_1 + 0.1x_2 \\ x_2^+ &= -0.1x_1 + x_2 + 0.1(1 - x_1^2)x_2 \end{aligned}$$

A typical trajectory of x_1 is shown in Figure 1. Notice that the period of the limit cycle is approximately seventy time steps. The corresponding phase portrait is shown in Figure 2.

We constructed a MEE filter with $G = [0, 1]'$, $Q = 0.1$, $R = 0.01$ and $\alpha = 0.5$. We started the model at $x(0) = [0.5, 0]'$ and the filter at $\hat{x}(0|0) = [1, 1]'$ and $\pi^0(x) = \|x - \hat{x}(0|0)\|^2/2$.

The error $\tilde{x}_1(t|t)$ is shown in Figure 3 and is essentially zero after about twenty time steps. In Figure 4 the phase portrait of $x(t)$ is in blue and that of $\hat{x}_1(t|t)$ is in red. Notice that $\hat{x}_1(t|t)$ converges to $x(t)$ faster than $x(t)$ converges to the limit cycle.

The computational time for each step of the filter was typically 1.1 seconds on a four year old laptop using nonoptimized code. This is comparable to time step of the model.

VIII. CONCLUSION

We have extended Minimum Energy Estimation of Mortenson [12] and Hijab [4] to discrete time systems and showed how power series method can be employed to lessen the computational burden. We believe that such techniques compliment standard Moving Horizon Estimation techniques for real time filtering of faster processes as they essentially reduce the horizon length to one time step.

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